

Walk the Yorke Map Assessment - Expert Assessment

This survey is intended for members of the Yorke Peninsula Council, other organizations with direct links to the trail, or individuals with specific knowledge in the areas of digital cartography/GIS, tourism, or trail management.

If you are a member of the general public (including Yorke Peninsula residents) please fill out [this survey instead](#).

We are researching effective cartography for tourism-focused participatory applications and would love your input! The aim of this project is to create a web map of the Walk the Yorke Trail in South Australia. The map is intended to be highly usable, suitable for a range of trail users, whilst also providing participatory functionality allowing users to share otherwise-inaccessible information with both other users and trail managers. We would appreciate your feedback on the design and interaction decisions we have made and your opinion on the suitability of this map. The map is still at the prototype stage so there will be a few bugs, and trail information is incomplete. The map can be found at <https://wtv.joshgore.com.au/>

This project has been approved by the University of South Australia's Human Research Ethics Committee. Please read the [Participant Information Sheet](#). By completing and submitting the survey, you are indicating that you have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and give your consent to be involved in the research.

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About You

1. Your Primary Background

- Cartography/GIS
- Tourism
- Environmental
- Trail Asset Management
- Other (please specify) - if you are a Yorke Peninsula resident and not part of an organisation involved with tourism or trail management please fill out the general survey.

2. Are you part of the Yorke Peninsula Council or another organization with direct links to the trail?

- Yes
- No

3. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Year 11 or below
- Year 12
- Technical or Trade Qualification
- Bachelor degree - in progress
- Bachelor degree
- Postgraduate degree (Masters or higher)
- Prefer not to say

4. Where do you live?

- Yorke Peninsula
- South Australia
- Other Australia
- Outside Australia

5. Your Age

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

6. Please rate your technical knowledge about digital maps

Very Low

Very High

7. Please rate your ability to adapt to new software

Very Low

Very High

8. Which browser(s) are you using to view the map?

- Chrome
- Firefox
- Microsoft Edge
- Internet Explorer (will not work)
- Safari
- Other (please specify)

9. You may conduct this survey whilst viewing the map on one or several different devices. Which devices are you viewing the map on?

- Desktop
- Laptop
- High end smartphone
- mid-range smartphone
- low end smartphone
- high end tablet
- mid-range tablet
- low-end tablet

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Cartography

Task 1. View a description of a trail section.

10. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

11. How effective was the side/bottom panel information presentation method?

Highly Ineffective

Highly Effective

12. Please provide some comments on your experiences completing this task...

Task 2. Find a toilet and an information sign on the map.

13. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

14. Did you find the scale-dependent cartographic approach effective? (i.e. more information appearing as you zoom in)

Very Ineffective

Very Effective

15. Would you prefer filters for limiting information shown?

Yes

No

Both (more information is displayed as you zoom in but you can turn off some features)

16. Please provide some comments about your experiences and views of the map design for completing this task...

Task 3. Determine which features are interactive and view information associated with an interactive point.

17. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

18. Was it clear how to interact with features?

Very Unclear

Very Clear

19. Was it clear which feature(s) were being queried?

Very Unclear

Very Clear

20. Do you have any comments on feature interactions?

Additional Cartographic Questions

21. How clear was the cartographic symbology?

Very Unclear

Very Clear

22. Do you have any general comments on cartography and design?

23. Do you have any symbology-specific comments?

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Participation and Information Sharing

Task 4. Review a stage. (create an account or use test1234 for username and password)

24. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

25. How useful would you consider the current review functionality for trail users?

Not Useful

Very Useful

26. If you have knowledge of this area, how useful would you consider the current review functionality for trail managers?

Not Useful

Very Useful

N/A

27. How can we improve the review interface and functionality for trail users?

28. How can we improve the review interface and functionality for trail managers?

Task 5. Share an issue with a trail shelter using the #issue tag in the comment box. (create an account or use test1234 for username and password)

29. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

30. Comments are updated real-time allowing live chats. How useful would you consider this functionality?

Not Useful

Very Useful

31. How effective would you consider the issue tagging method (it could be used for further categories)?

Very Ineffective

Very Effective

32. How can we improve the comment interface and functionality?

Task 6. Add a hazard point to the map (create an account or use test1234 for username and password)

33. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

34. How can the point sharing interface be improved?

Additional participation functionality questions

35. Do you have any general comments on the participatory functionality?

36. Do you think this map app could provide an effective platform for encouraging users to submit information to assist research and management projects (e.g. with advertisement of the trail project in the splash screen)?

37. What other participatory functionality should be included in this map? (reason and priority would be great!)

44. If you viewed the map on multiple devices, how would you rate it's adaption to these different devices?

Very Poor

Very Good

A horizontal Likert scale consisting of five radio buttons arranged in a row on a light gray background. The buttons are evenly spaced and represent a scale from 'Very Poor' on the left to 'Very Good' on the right.

45. Are there any mobile or desktop specific cartographic interactions or adaptations which should be added?

46. Please provide your email address if you would like a one-page summary of the research findings emailed to you (this will occur in early December).

Email Address

Thanks for your time!